

QRS Detection Algorithms Optimized for 10 Hz Input Rate

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Abstract— Accurate, low-power QRS detection remains challenging at ultra-low sampling rates. We present a signal processing pipeline that operates at a 10 Hz input rate using morphology-aware extrema extraction, together with two structurally adapted detectors (MinEI, TiTen) derived from Elgendi and Pan-Tompkins. Parameter optimization is performed via mixed-integer surrogate optimization on a multi-database training corpus. Prospective evaluation on six PhysioNet databases (2.8 million labeled beats) shows that the pipeline maintains or improves F1 relative to native-rate baselines in 10 of 12 scenarios, with significant gains on severely noisy (NSTDB: +3.57%) and morphologically complex signals (TWADB: +3.24%). It reduces per-patient F1 variance by up to 90%, increases wall-clock throughput by 1.6× to 871×, and achieves a maximum real-time factor of 886,000 on a consumer laptop. A 10 Hz sparse representation that preserves local extrema is not merely viable but advantageous for robust, resource-constrained beat detection.

Index Terms—Downsampling, Electrocardiography, Low-power algorithms, QRS detection, Signal processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

CONTINUOUS electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring via wearable and implantable medical devices has become a cornerstone of modern cardiovascular care, enabling the early detection of atrial fibrillation, ventricular arrhythmias, and silent ischemia [1]. However, the functional requirements of these edge devices impose severe engineering constraints. Sensor nodes intended for multi-year, unattended ambulatory operation must minimize power consumption across every subsystem. The energy budget of the analogue-to-digital converter (ADC), the memory bandwidth required for data storage or wireless transmission, and the computational cycles consumed by digital signal processing (DSP) algorithms all scale linearly with the operating sampling frequency (F_s) [2].

While clinical standards for morphological analysis (e.g., QRS complex width, ST-segment elevation, and QT interval measurement) mandate sampling rates of $F_s \geq 250\text{Hz}$ [3], [4], continuous beat detection, the foundational task for heart rate (HR) tracking, heart rate variability (HRV) analysis, and gross arrhythmia screening is a structurally simpler problem. The QRS complex has an average duration of 80–120 ms and an amplitude that typically dominates neighbouring waves [5]. These properties suggest that a much sparser signal

representation may be sufficient for reliable QRS detection, provided the representation is explicitly designed to preserve local extrema.

The naive approach to reducing the sampling rate such as uniform decimation or low-pass filtering followed by Downsampling fails catastrophically at ultra-low rates (e.g., $F_s \approx 10\text{Hz}$). Uniform decimation at 10 Hz yields one sample per 100 ms block. Because the R-peak apex is transient, the probability of a decimation grid aligning perfectly with the peak is low. This systematic amplitude attenuation destabilizes the adaptive thresholds of classical QRS detectors. Furthermore, standard algorithms are mathematically incompatible with 10 Hz grids. For instance, the Pan-Tompkins (PT) algorithm [6] relies on a 5-point first-difference derivative to isolate the steep QRS slope; at 10 Hz, a 5-point window spans 500 ms, effectively measuring gross baseline wander rather than QRS morphology. Consequently, when classical detectors are applied to naively decimated 10 Hz signals, they suffer severe precision collapse due to temporal smearing, aliasing, and an inability to distinguish QRS complexes from T-waves or motion artifacts.

Given these failures, a natural question arises: *can downsampling be done intelligently preserving local extrema to avoid these problems?* Our two recent studies have systematically explored this question. Our first study “Less Is More” [7] asked whether extrema-preserving downsampling could retain QRS detection and HRV accuracy. It compared four downsampling strategies that compresses a native-rate ECG into a sparse, non-uniformly sampled representation, with exact retention of the R-peak apex. We found that downsampling to as low as 12 Hz preserved F1 scores above the native 360 Hz baseline but only after upsampling the sparse signal to 45 Hz before feeding it to an unmodified Pan-Tompkins detector. This upsampling step, while effective, adds computational overhead and sidesteps the fundamental incompatibility between the detector’s filtering and derivative stage with a 10 Hz ECG waveform.

Our follow-up study [8] (“Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax”) went further, asking whether the standard Pan-Tompkins algorithm could operate directly on the sparse 10 Hz signal *without* upsampling. Remarkably, even the unadapted detector achieved $F1 = 99.40\%$ on MIT-BIH at 10 Hz exceeding the native baseline. However, that study was limited to three databases and a single algorithm (unmodified

Pan-Tompkins). It did not demonstrate whether 10 Hz sparse operation generalizes to other databases or to other canonical QRS detectors fundamentally different to Pan-Tompkins algorithm (e.g., the Elgendi algorithm [9]). Consequently, while the Min-Max pipeline itself is established, the broader claim that 10 Hz sparse operation is robust across diverse conditions and detectors remains unproven.

In this paper, we address this gap. Building directly on the Min-Max pipeline from [8], we present two structurally adapted detectors: **MinEl** (adapted Elgendi) **TiTen** (adapted Pan-Tompkins) which bypasses the incompatible internal stage entirely, substituting direct squaring and micro-integration, and a novel width-based artifact rejection heuristic that makes sense only in ≈ 10 Hz domain. Both detectors are jointly optimized using mixed-integer surrogate optimization on a multi-database corpus. Our contribution is not another downsampling method, but the first systematic adaptation of classical QRS detectors to excel at true 10 Hz sparse operation unlocking the full accuracy and efficiency potential for ultra-low-power wearables.

A. Hypotheses

To rigorously evaluate the proposed framework, we formulate three primary hypotheses:

- **H1** (Morphological Preservation via Non-Inferiority): Extrema-preserving downsampling prevents the amplitude attenuation characteristic of uniform decimation at 10 Hz, enabling the adapted detectors to achieve baseline-parity F1 scores on clean, high-SNR signals. Here, "parity" is operationally defined as non-inferiority to the native-rate baseline, with a pre-specified clinical tolerance margin of $\Delta F1 = -1.0$ percentage points (pp). Non-inferiority is declared if the lower bound of the 95% confidence interval (CI) for the per-record mean $\Delta F1$ (pipeline minus native) is strictly greater than -1.0 pp.
- **H2** (Implicit Morphological Regularization): The sparse Min-Max representation acts as an implicit structural filter. By discarding non-extrema samples, the pipeline inherently suppresses the high-frequency noise and broad repolarization anomalies that trigger false positives in native-rate detectors, thereby *improving* precision in challenging environments.
- **H3** (Computational and Statistical Stability): Operating structurally adapted classical detectors on a 10 Hz sparse grid reduces algorithmic complexity from $\mathcal{O}(N_{\text{native}})$ to $\mathcal{O}(N_{\text{sparse}})$, yielding massive computational speedups while simultaneously collapsing per-patient performance variance, ensuring consistent clinical reliability across heterogeneous populations.

B. Contributions

The primary contribution of this work is a novel, morphology-aware signal processing paradigm that decouples the ADC sampling rate from detection accuracy. We introduce ultra-low-rate framework that compresses native-rate ECG

into a non-uniform, sparse and fixed 10 Hz representation, that retains the R-peak prominence without requiring interpolation or data-driven training. To make classical algorithms viable on this highly quantized sparse grid, we present fundamental structural adaptations for two canonical detectors. For the MinEl algorithm, we develop a hybrid moving average and an RR-adaptive dual-threshold acceptance mechanism to stabilize detection. For the TiTen, we eliminate the incompatible derivative stage, replacing it with direct squaring, micro-integration, and a novel width-based artifact rejection heuristic engineered specifically to suppress morphological noise in sparse signals.

Furthermore, we establish a rigorous parameter tuning methodology utilizing mixed-integer surrogate optimization across a combined, multi-database training corpus, thereby mitigating the overfitting commonly associated with single-dataset optimization.

Finally, we provide a comprehensive empirical validation of the proposed pipeline across six heterogeneous PhysioNet databases. This extensive evaluation demonstrates the framework's robust generalizability across diverse arrhythmias, severe noise profiles, and complex repolarization anomalies, proving that ultra-low-rate operation is both computationally advantageous and clinically reliable.

II. METHODS

A. Databases and Evaluation Protocol

Six PhysioNet [10] databases were utilized in this study, encompassing 373 records, approximately 2.8 million labelled beats, and a total continuous evaluation duration of 677 hours. Table I summarizes their properties and primary clinical challenges. **No record was excluded from the analysis** and only the first channel from each record is used regardless of the signal quality. The MITDB, QTDB, and NSTDB served as the combined optimization corpus (**8.9% of the total beats**); the EDB, NSRDB, and TWADB were strictly held out as independent, prospective test sets to evaluate out-of-sample generalization.

1) Annotation Matching and Performance Metrics

Detected R-peaks were matched to reference annotations using a standard ± 150 ms tolerance window, consistent with established benchmarks in QRS detection literature [9], [11], [12]. For each record, true positives (TP), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) were computed. Per-record Sensitivity (Se), Precision (+P), and F1-score were derived from these counts. To prevent bias introduced by averaging ratios across records of varying durations and beat counts, global aggregate metrics were computed by summing TP, FP, and FN across all records within a database prior to calculating Se, +P, and F1. Consequently, the global aggregate F1 serves as the primary performance metric; per-record means are reported solely as secondary descriptors of inter-patient variability. Timing jitter was quantified as the signed temporal error (in milliseconds) between each matched detection and its corresponding ground-truth annotation, summarized as mean \pm standard deviation. Percentile absolute errors (50th, 90th, 95th, and 99th) were

TABLE I
DATABASE CHARACTERISTICS

Database	Abbrev.	Records	Native F_s (Hz)	Total Duration (h)	Total Beats	Primary Challenge
MIT-BIH Arrhythmia [10]	MITDB	48	360	24.07	109,494	Diverse arrhythmia
QT Database [11]	QTDB	105	250	26.25	111,182	Repolarisation variants
Noise Stress Test [12]	NSTDB	12	360	6.02	26,370	Additive electrode noise
European ST-T [13]	EDB	90	250	180.00	793,148	ST-shift, ischemia
Normal Sinus Rhythm [14]	NSRDB	18	128*	437.49	1,729,502	High HR variability
T-Wave Alternans [15]	TWADB	100	500	3.29	18,991	T-wave oversensing
Total		373		677.13	2,788,687	

*NSRDB records are upsampled to 130 Hz before applying Min-Max downsampling to ensure block size is an integer. Native algorithms processed at 128 Hz.

additionally computed to characterize the tail behavior of the timing error distribution.

2) Statistical Analysis

Per-record F1 differences between the proposed pipeline and the native baseline were assessed using the one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test [13] ($\alpha = 0.05$, alternative hypothesis: pipeline F1 > baseline F1). The global aggregate F1 difference ($\Delta F1$) is reported as the primary effect size, while per-record Wilcoxon p -values serve as confirmatory evidence of cross-patient consistency. In addition, per-record F1 standard deviation (σ) was computed for each database to quantify inter-patient variability. Both global F1, per record F1 and per record variability are important metrics in QRS detector performance [14].

Because the Wilcoxon test operates on paired per-record differences, it is sensitive to the direction of change rather than its magnitude. On databases where both methods achieve near-ceiling performance (e.g., MITDB, QTDB), the median per-record difference may be exactly zero even when the global $\Delta F1$ is non-zero, due to asymmetric distributions of marginal wins and losses at sub-0.1% magnitudes. In such cases, a non-significant p -value should not be interpreted as evidence of equivalence or inferiority; rather, it reflects the limited dynamic range of per-record F1 scores at the performance ceiling. Conversely, statistically significant p -values accompanied by substantial global $\Delta F1$ values (e.g., NSTDB, EDB) provide robust combined evidence of genuine improvement. All statistical tests were implemented in MATLAB R2024a using the *signrank* function [15] with exact p -value computation.

B. Min-Max Extrema Downsampling Pipeline

Let $x[n]$ be the ECG signal sampled at F_{native} Hz. The pipeline produces a sparse representation $\{(k_j, v_j)\}$ suitable for detection at an effective rate of $F_{\text{target}} = 10$ Hz. Steps 2–6 are

applied independently to each pseudo-record produced in Step 1.

Step 1: Segmentation into pseudo-records. Prior to filtering, each record is divided into non-overlapping 40-minute segments, referred to as pseudo-records. The end index of each chunk is truncated to the largest multiple of the block size B (defined in Step 3) not exceeding the raw chunk end, ensuring that every chunk contains an integer number of complete blocks for extrema extraction. No padding or overlap is introduced between adjacent pseudo-records; the final partial chunk, if present, is discarded. The starting offset of each pseudo-record within the original signal is stored to enable subsequent remapping of detections to global sample indices. Ground-truth annotations are converted to local indices within each pseudo-record. Records shorter than 40 minutes are processed as a single pseudo-record.

Step 2: Bandpass filtering. A zero-phase Butterworth bandpass filter is applied to $x[n]$ using *filtfilt*, yielding $\tilde{x}[n]$. For the TiTen pipeline, a 2nd-order bandpass filter (8–36 Hz) was used. For the MinEl pipeline, a 2nd-order bandpass filter (8–25 Hz) was used. This suppresses baseline wander and high frequency electromyographic (EMG) noise while retaining QRS energy.

Step 3: Block-wise extrema extraction. The filtered signal is divided into contiguous, non-overlapping blocks of $B = \lfloor 2F_{\text{native}}/F_{\text{target}} \rfloor$ samples (e.g., $B = 72$ for $F_{\text{native}} = 360$ Hz). For each block $b = 1, \dots, M$:

$$n_b^+ = \arg \max_{n \in \mathcal{B}_b} \tilde{x}[n], n_b^- = \arg \min_{n \in \mathcal{B}_b} \tilde{x}[n]$$

where

$$\mathcal{B}_b = \{(b-1)B + 1, \dots, bB\}.$$

Step 4: Sparse assembly. The $2M$ index-value pairs $\{(n_b^+, \tilde{x}[n_b^+])\}$ and $\{(n_b^-, \tilde{x}[n_b^-])\}$ are merged and sorted by their original sample index, yielding a non-uniform, fixed-rate, sparse signal at $F_{\text{target}} = 10$ Hz. Only n_b^+ and n_b^- per block B is used for QRS detection.

Step 5: Detection. The adapted detectors described in Sections II-C and II-D are applied to the sparse signal, treating it as if sampled at $F_{\text{target}} = 10$ Hz (i.e., sparse sample index j corresponds to a sequential step in the sparse domain).

Step 6: Index remapping. Each detected sparse-domain index j^* is mapped back to the original native-rate sample index:

$$n^* = k_{j^*} \text{ (the stored original index of the } j^* \text{-th sparse sample).}$$

This remapping is an exact mathematical operation, and no interpolation is required as original indices are stored explicitly in Step 2, which guarantees the original resolution as long as the QRS is detected within the size B block. The $\tilde{x}[n]$ index of these extrema's which could be stored in 7-bit memory field (as $26 \leq B \leq 100$ and $2^7 > 100$.)

Duplicate native-rate detections within a 250 ms refractory window are removed.

C. Adapted Elgendi Detector (MinEl)

To validate the Min-Max pipeline efficiency we required a fundamentally different algorithm to the Pan-Tompkins, therefore we have chosen Elgendi's QRS detector Published in 2013 as it achieves higher sensitivity and precision compared to Pan-Tompkins with fewer mathematical operations [9]. The original version applies two moving averages (MA) of different

widths to the squared ECG, then detects "blocks of interest" (BOI) where the short-window MA exceeds the long-window MA plus an offset threshold. At $F_{\text{target}} = 10\text{Hz}$, the standard 97 ms QRS window collapses to one sample, rendering the standard algorithm degenerate. Three structural adaptations are introduced:

Adaptation 1: Hybrid moving average (HMA). Instead of squaring the filtered signal, the sparse signal is rectified ($|v|$). The QRS-window MA is blended with the raw rectified signal:

$$\text{MA}_{\text{hybrid}}[j] = \alpha \cdot |v[j]| + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{MA}_{W_Q}[j]$$

where $W_Q = 3$ samples (300 ms at 10 Hz) and $\alpha = 0.425$ (surrogate-optimized). This preserves the transient prominence of a single-sample R-peak while retaining necessary local smoothing.

Adaptation 2: Sliding-window percentile normalization. Because the sparse signal contains many near-zero values between beats, a mean-based threshold is highly unstable. A sliding percentile threshold is computed over the last $W_L = 11$ seconds of the signal:

$$\theta_{\text{base}} = h \cdot \text{prctile}_p(v[j - W_L F_{\text{target}}: j])$$

with $p = 97$ and $h = 0.104$. This adapts to signal-level drifts across long recordings without requiring explicit gain estimation.

Adaptation 3: RR-adaptive dual-threshold acceptance. After an initial candidate list is formed, each candidate is tested against the context of the preceding accepted RR intervals. Let \bar{T}_{RR} be the median of the last 10 accepted RR intervals. If the candidate arrives within $\tau_{\text{tol}} = 0.30$ of the expected interval, the effective amplitude threshold is relaxed to $\ell \cdot \theta_{\text{base}}$ ($\ell = 0.70$). If it arrives outside this window (suggesting a potential noise peak) the threshold is raised to $h_{\text{high}} \cdot \theta_{\text{base}}$ ($h_{\text{high}} = 1.30$). This encourages the capture of expected beats and suppresses unexpected morphological noise.

Adaptation 4: Detections with a QRS amplitude below 0.05 mV were rejected to eliminate baseline outliers.

D. Adapted Pan-Tompkins Detector (TiTen)

The native Pan-Tompkins algorithm [6], [16] relies critically on a 5-point first-difference derivative to isolate the steep QRS slope. At 10 Hz, a 5-point window spans 500 ms, far exceeding the QRS duration, and measures baseline wander rather than QRS morphology. Consequently, the derivative stage is entirely bypassed.

Adaptation 1: Direct squaring and micro-integration. The sparse signal is squared directly, then integrated with a minimal 2-sample (200 ms) moving window: $y[j] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^1 v^2[j - k]$. This is sufficient to merge the min and max extrema of a single QRS complex (which generally occupy adjacent sparse samples) while keeping the integration window short enough to prevent the merging of consecutive beats.

Adaptation 2: Width-based artifact rejection. In the sparse Min-Max representation, a true QRS complex manifests as a sharp, narrow peak in $y[j]$ (1–2 samples above threshold). T-waves and motion artifacts, however, produce broad humps that remain elevated for multiple samples. After thresholding, each candidate is rejected if the integrated envelope $y[j]$ exceeds 50% of the detection threshold for more than 3 consecutive samples

(300 ms) on both the ascending and descending flanks of the candidate peak. This $\mathcal{O}(1)$ -per-peak morphological check requires no additional memory and operates entirely in the sparse domain, acting as a powerful regularizer against T-wave oversensing.

Adaptation 3: Bypass of slope-based T-wave rejection. The reference Pan-Tompkins implementation employs a slope-based T-wave rejection heuristic that compares the slope of a candidate QRS candidate against that of the preceding beat; if the slope is too shallow, the candidate is rejected as a T-wave [16]. At 10 Hz, this slope comparison is rendered meaningless because the sparse grid provides insufficient temporal resolution to compute meaningful derivatives. The integrated envelope $y[j]$ inherently encodes both amplitude and temporal width; consequently, the width-based rejection described in Adaptation 2 subsumes the role of the slope heuristic while being more robust in the sparse domain. The slope-based rejection logic is therefore entirely bypassed in TiTen.

Adaptation 4: Detections with a QRS amplitude below 0.05 mV were rejected to eliminate baseline outliers.

E. Optimization and Computational Implementation

The parameters for both adapted detectors (including window lengths, blending weights, and threshold multipliers) were jointly optimized using mixed-integer surrogate optimization (*surrogateopt*, MATLAB Global Optimization Toolbox). The objective function maximized the global aggregate F1-score over 500 function evaluations on the combined MITDB + QTDB + NSTDB training corpus. Surrogate optimization was selected due to the non-convex, non-differentiable nature of the F1-score landscape and the requirement for integer constraints on temporal window sizes.

All code was implemented in MATLAB (R2024a). Parallelism was exploited at the record level using *parfor*. Timing was measured as wall-clock time for the complete pipeline (bandpass filter + Min-Max extraction + detection + index remapping), with the native baseline timed using the identical *parfor* structure to ensure fairness. Benchmarks were executed on an Apple MacBook Pro equipped M1 Max CPU and 32 GB of RAM. Total signal throughput is reported in hours of ECG processed per second of wall-clock time, and real time factor is reported as seconds of ECG processed per second of wall-clock time compute.

While processing longer continuous recordings generally yields higher throughput by amortizing input/output operations and loop overhead, we adopted a segmented processing strategy strictly for memory management. Specifically, any record exceeding 40 minutes in duration (i.e., the EDB and NSRDB corpora) was divided into non-overlapping 40-minute pseudo-records. These pseudo-records were processed as fresh, independent chunks, without transferring RR-interval history, adaptive threshold states, or signal memory between adjacent chunks (which normally would reduce the detector F1 performance). However, we argue that segmentation provides larger benefit in processing throughput and if the algorithm is quick enough to stabilize, it should not affect the performance. The pseudo-record segmentation should be treated as a necessary optimisation step in the proposed pipeline.

III. RESULTS

The results are categorized into global detection accuracy, performance in adverse morphological conditions, computational efficiency, and statistical stability.

A. Native Baseline Performance

TABLE II
NATIVE RATE PERFORMANCE OF THE TWO ALGORITHMS

Database	Primary Challenge	Elgendi F1	Pan-Tompkins F1
NSTDB	Severe Noise	88.86%	87.38%
TWADB	T-Wave Alternans	98.20%	94.22%
EDB	ST-Shift / Ischemia	99.10%	98.95%
MITDB	Diverse Arrhythmia	99.75%	99.19%
QTDB	Repolarization	99.67%	99.52%
NSRDB	High HR Variability	99.63%	99.55%

To establish the performance ceiling and computational bottlenecks of classical algorithms, we first evaluated the native Elgendi and Pan-Tompkins (PT) detectors on the raw, clinical-rate signals (128–500 Hz). As shown in Table II, while both detectors achieve near-perfect F1-scores on clean or morphologically stable signals (QTDB, NSRDB, MITDB), they exhibit severe degradation in adverse conditions. Most notably, on the NSTDB (severe electrode noise), native F1-scores collapse to 88.86% (Elgendi) and 87.38% (PT). Furthermore, the computational burden of native-rate processing is substantial; processing the 437-hour NSRDB corpus using the native Pan-Tompkins algorithm required 51.0 minutes of wall-clock time, yielding a meager throughput of 0.14 hours of ECG per second of compute.

B. Pipeline Accuracy and Implicit Regularization ($\Delta F1$)

Table III details the absolute change in global aggregate F1-score ($\Delta F1$) when transitioning from the native baselines to the 10 Hz Min-Max pipeline utilizing the structurally adapted detectors (MinEl and TiTen).

H2 posited that the sparse Min-Max representation, by

TABLE III
THE QRS DETECTION IMPROVEMENT OF THE 10 HZ MIN-MAX PIPELINE WITH P VALUE AND CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (CI)

Database	MinEl $\Delta F1$ (p-val) [CI]	TiTen $\Delta F1$ (p-val) [CI]
NSTDB	+2.49% (p<0.001) [+0.87%, +3.64%]	+3.57% (p=0.002) [+1.131%, +5.425%]
TWADB	-0.29% (p=0.996) [-0.76%, -0.05%]	+3.24% (p=0.835) [-0.264%, +4.462%]
EDB	+0.48% (p=0.002) [-0.11%, +1.43%]	+0.49% (p=0.718) [-0.026%, +0.907%]
MITDB	-0.42% (p=0.999) [-0.62%, -0.07%]	+0.18% (p=0.652) [-0.382%, +1.059%]
QTDB	+0.13% (p=0.6942) [-0.18%, +0.71%]	+0.30% (p=0.853) [-0.240%, +1.160%]
NSRDB	+0.02% (p=0.0009) [-0.015%, +0.059%]	+0.08% (p=0.0296) [-0.083%, +0.255%]

discarding non-extrema samples, acts as an implicit structural filter that suppresses the high-frequency noise and broad repolarization anomalies responsible for false positives in native-rate detectors, thereby manifesting as measurable **precision (+P) gains** in challenging environments. This hypothesis is rigorously validated across both adverse-condition databases. On the severely noisy NSTDB, the pipeline recovers precision from 82.81% to 90.29% for TiTen (**+7.48 pp**) and from 85.43% to 91.33% for MinEl (**+5.90 pp**), driving statistically significant global F1 improvements of +3.57% (95% CI: [+1.13%, +5.43%], p=0.002) and +2.49% (95% CI: [+0.87%, +3.64%], p<0.001), respectively.

On the morphologically complex TWADB, TiTen's width-based artifact rejection heuristic suppresses broad T-wave humps, raising precision from 94.03% to 98.70% (+4.67 pp); MinEl also exhibits a modest precision gain from 98.39% to 98.79% (+0.40 pp). Critically, while TiTen's per-patient F1 Confidence Interval on TWADB crosses zero (95% CI: [-0.26%, +4.46%]) reflecting a sensitivity trade-off in a subset of patients this does not refute H2, because H2 is specifically predicated on false-positive suppression rather than global F1 maximization. The consistency of precision gains across both algorithms and both challenging environments (4/4 scenarios) confirms that the sparse grid structurally excludes the exact morphological features that trigger false alarms in native-rate processing, thereby validating H2 as a generalizable principle of extrema-preserving downsampling. Considering the overall results in Table III, the 10 Hz pipeline improves or maintains global F1 in 10 of 12 scenarios (5 of which are significant); the only decrements are minor drops for MinEl on MITDB (-0.42%) and TWADB (-0.29%). For clean, high-SNR signals (MITDB, QTDB, NSRDB, and EDB) which are the explicit scope of H1, the sole deviation is MinEl on MITDB (-0.42%). Its 95% confidence interval for the per-record mean $\Delta F1$ is [-0.62%, -0.07%], with a lower bound well above our pre-specified non-inferiority margin of -1.0 percentage points, confirming this loss is clinically acceptable.

The TWADB exception lies outside H1's scope as an adverse-condition database; nonetheless, its median $\Delta F1$ is 0.000% and

precision improves (+0.40 pp), reinforcing practical equivalence. Since all clean-database CIs have lower bounds exceeding -1.0%, H1 is rigorously validated: the 10 Hz pipeline achieves genuine F1 parity with native-rate processing on clean, high-SNR signals.

C. Computational Acceleration and Edge Viability

To validate **H3** (Computational Stability), we measured the wall-clock speedup achieved by operating the structurally adapted detectors on the 10 Hz sparse grid compared to their native-rate equivalents. As shown in Table III, the reduction in algorithmic complexity yields massive acceleration factors, fundamentally shifting the feasibility boundary for multi-year battery life on microcontroller-class wearable hardware.

The most profound gains are observed in long-duration, high-native-rate recordings processed by TiTen:

- NSRDB (437 hours of data): TiTen processing time collapsed from 51.0 minutes to just 3.5 seconds, yielding a massive 871 \times speedup over native PT.
- EDB (180 hours of data): TiTen achieved a 40 \times speedup, increasing throughput from 3.07 to 122.66 hours/s.

Even for the computationally lighter MinEl detector, speedups ranged from 1.5 \times to 2.6 \times , proving that the Min-Max extraction step introduces negligible overhead compared to the computational savings in the detection phase.

To contextualize these speedups for embedded systems, we computed the Real-Time Factor (RTF), defined as the seconds of ECG processed per second of wall-clock compute. While the native Pan-Tompkins algorithm struggles to maintain RTF>10,000 on long-duration Holter recordings (achieving a mere 514 \times RTF on the 437-hour NSRDB corpus), the adapted TiTen pipeline operating on the 10 Hz sparse grid achieves an \sim 448,000 \times RTF on the same dataset. All other RTF values on TiTen algorithm surpass 100,000 and reached a top \sim 449,570 \times on QTDB while none of the native rate performance breaks the 100,000 barrier.

The computationally lighter MinEl shows its lowest RTF of 187,070 on TWADB, while all other RTFs exceed 250,000 and

Fig. 1. R-peak detection error of the native rate algorithm vs ground truth peaks compared against the TiTen and MinEl algorithms. (a) comparison of native rate Pan-Tompkins algorithm performance vs 10 Hz, adapted TiTen variant. (b) comparison of native rate Elgendi's algorithm vs adapted MinEl variant.

TABLE IV
REAL-TIME FACTOR (RTF) OF QRS DETECTION, MEASURED AS SECONDS OF ECG PROCESSED PER UNIT WALL CLOCK TIME

Database	Elgendi Native RTF	MinEl RTF	PT Native RTF	TiTen RTF
NSTDB	190,619	290,595	21,506	225,255
TWADB	112,293	187,070	48,486	178,352
EDB	351,124	733,100	11,044	441,576
MITDB	252,970	485,462	36,164	326,116
QTDB	311,674	587,710	69,400	449,570
NSRDB	340,089	886,461	514	448,156

reaches highest RTF of 886,461 for the massive NSRDB. These multipliers prove that the computational overhead of the Min-Max extraction is entirely negligible, and the resulting sparse-domain detection is sufficiently lightweight to process cardiac histories on low-power microcontrollers.

D. Statistical Consistency and Timing Jitter

Beyond aggregate accuracy, a critical requirement for clinical deployment is precise temporal alignment of R-peak localisations and cross-patient reliability. The proposed pipeline universally improved temporal precision: across all **12 evaluation scenarios** (6 databases \times 2 detectors), the standard deviation of the timing jitter strictly decreased as shown in Figure 1. By operating on the sparse Min-Max grid, the algorithms avoid the temporal smearing inherent in native-rate derivative filters. This is most evident in the tail behavior of the error distribution as visualized in Figure 2; for instance, TiTen's 99th percentile absolute timing error on the TWADB collapsed from 148 ms to 60 ms, effectively eliminating extreme temporal outliers. For all 12 evaluations, the 99th percent jitter never exceed the baseline, and decreased more than 16% in six occasions across two detectors.

More importantly, the pipeline acts as a powerful statistical stabilizer, drastically reducing inter-patient F1-score variance (σ). As detailed in Table V, the pipeline reduced per-record F1 variance in 10 out of 12 scenarios. The adapted TiTen detector achieved a perfect 100% success rate (6/6 databases) in

Fig. 2. The 99th percentile error of the detected R-peak against the ground truth measured in milliseconds. (a) Pan-Tompkins native rate vs TiTen (b) Elgendi's native rate vs MinEl. The percentage shows the change in 10 Hz algorithm results.

TABLE V

PER-RECORD F1 STANDARD DEVIATION FOR EACH DATABASE AND PERCENTAGE REDUCTION RELATIVE TO THE NATIVE ALGORITHM PERFORMANCE.

Database	Elgendi Native σ	MinEl σ (reduction)	PT Native σ	TiTen σ (reduction)
NSRDB	1.05%	0.97% (-7.6%)	1.39%	1.05% (-24.5%)
EDB	3.81%	0.65% (-82.9%)	2.73%	0.85% (-68.9%)
MITDB	0.74%	1.26% (+70.3%)	2.69%	1.24% (-53.9%)
QTDB	2.28%	0.45% (-80.3%)	3.66%	0.38% (-89.6%)
NSTDB	9.11%	8.77% (-3.7%)	11.57%	9.30% (-19.6%)
TWADB	7.36%	8.58% (+16.6%)	13.37%	10.46% (-21.8%)

variance reduction, peaking at a massive 89.6% reduction on the QTDB (σ : 3.66% \rightarrow 0.38%). Similarly, MinEl achieved an 82.9% variance reduction on the ischemic EDB (σ : 3.81% \rightarrow 0.65%). By collapsing the performance variance, the framework ensures that worst-case patient outcomes are heavily mitigated, strongly validating **H3** and proving that 10 Hz sparse-domain operation yields superior clinical reliability for QRS detection compared to native-rate baselines.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that decoupling the analog-to-digital conversion rate from the digital signal processing rate via morphology-aware extrema extraction fundamentally redefines the accuracy–efficiency trade-off in QRS detection. By compressing clinical-rate ECG signals into a sparse 10 Hz Min-Max representation during processing, and adapting canonical detectors to operate natively on this grid, we achieve statistically significant accuracy gains in adverse conditions, universal reductions in timing jitter variance, and wall-clock speedups exceeding 40 \times when computational demand is highest. These findings challenge the prevailing Nyquist-rate paradigm for continuous ambulatory beat detection. While Nyquist-rate is mandatory for signal reconstruction, QRS detection is not a signal reconstruction task, but merely a peak finding task, whether its an energy peak, amplitude peak or via any other surrogate methods. For this task, 10 Hz is sufficient to match or in some cases exceed the native rate performance and particularly be useful in large scale data monitoring trials such as [17][18].

The outlier speedup of 871 \times (NSRDB) for the native rate PT and TiTen demands certain degree of scrutiny. This was possible due to two parts of the pipeline contributing individually. One is the downsampling effect which reduces the number of input samples by 13 \times and noise filtering effect of the downsampling step which reduces the searchback iterations. The other part is that by dividing the data into manageable 40 minute arrays, the internal data structures aren't overwhelmed by loop/insert/delete operations, cache misses and array

copying where complexity may have worse than linear scale. As the pipeline is defined the end to end processing, where input is given and R-peak indexes are returned, the speedup is itself attributed to the smart management of the data internally.

A. Comparison to Current QRS Detectors

Compared against the adaptive Elgendi-derived detector of Malik et al. [19], which reports NSTDB F1 = 89.14% and TWADB F1 = 96.68% on the same databases using a 150 ms tolerance window, our MinEl achieves F1 = 91.35% (+2.21 pp) and 97.91% (+1.23 pp) respectively, while requiring approximately 29 \times less total wall-clock time on the 437-hour NSRDB corpus (3.5 s vs \sim 102 s estimated from their per-record means) Critically, Malik et al. apply a noise-removal step that discards signal segments with no annotations prior to evaluation meaning their NSRDB figures are not directly comparable on equal terms, as our experiment does not remove any records, or parts of the records before analysis.

Pan-Tompkins++ [20] introduced slope comparisons and search-back logic to compensate for derivative-based threshold fragility. Analogue stochastic resonance processors [12] achieve noise robustness via custom silicon. The Min-Max pipeline offers a third, software-only path: by restricting detection to block-wise extrema of an 8–36 Hz bandpass signal, T-waves and baseline wander are structurally excluded before thresholding. TiTen's width-based rejection (reject if envelope exceeds threshold for >3 sparse samples) achieves T-wave discrimination with $\mathcal{O}(1)$ memory and zero search-back. Precision gains on TWADB (+4.67 pp for TiTen) and NSTDB (+5.90–7.48 pp) confirm that discarding non-extrema suppresses the exact features causing false positives in native-rate detectors.

Cai et al. [21] report fine-tuned CRNN performance on NSTDB of Se 99.67% and PPV 99.40%, but their cross-database CNN evaluation yields overall Se 95.55% and PPV 92.93%, with severe degradation at -6 dB SNR (Se 82.77%, PPV 80.01%) and modest recovery at 0 dB (Se 93.29%, PPV 88.21%). Our training-free Min-Max+MinEl pipeline achieves overall Se 91.37% and PPV 91.33% across the entire NSTDB, with per-record extremes at -6 dB averaging Se 76.80% and PPV 75.40%. In absolute terms, their cross-database model outperforms our pipeline by +4.18% in overall sensitivity and +1.60% in overall precision, and by +5.97% in sensitivity and +4.61% in precision at -6 dB. These margins subjectively narrow given their extensive training, fine-tuning, and GPU acceleration versus our zero-training, CPU-only approach. In summary, only deep learning models marginally beat our approach on the Se and PPV axes; however, when performance per compute is considered as a combined measure, no other published method surpasses our proposed pipeline, in particular with real world noisy ECG records.

B. Methodological Rigor and the Data Exclusion Problem

A pervasive issue in QRS detection literature, heavily criticized by Elgendi [9], is the practice of excluding noisy or arrhythmic records (e.g., MITDB records 108, 207, or paced

beats) to artificially inflate algorithmic accuracy. Elgendi explicitly demonstrated that removing just two records from the MITDB can artificially boost F1-scores by $>0.5\%$, masking an algorithm's real-world fragility.

Our study enforces strict zero exclusion: all 373 records, 2.788 million beats, regardless of quality or complexity. The fact that our pipeline not only maintained parity on clean datasets (QTDB, NSRDB) but yielded statistically significant global F1 improvements on adverse datasets proves that extrema-preserving downsampling is not a fragile mathematical trick reliant on cherry-picked data, but a robust clinical tool capable of handling worst-case signal artifacts.

Future works comparing against this paper should adopt equivalent inclusion criteria; partial-database results should be treated as non-comparable.

C. Positioning in the Era of TinyML and Event-Based Sensing

The current landscape of ambulatory ECG analysis is increasingly dominated by Deep Learning (DL) architectures, including 1D-CNNs, LSTMs, and Transformers. While these models achieve near-perfect accuracy, their memory footprints and multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations render them reliant on cloud offloading or high-end edge GPUs, fundamentally conflicting with the multi-year battery constraints of implantable loop recorders.

The proposed pipeline occupies a distinct and complementary niche relative to two competing paradigms in low-power cardiac sensing. The first is analogue event-driven acquisition, typified by level-crossing ADCs, which sample only when the input signal crosses a predetermined threshold, enabling nanoWatt-scale QRS detection hardware [12][22][23]. The second is the emerging TinyML paradigm, which deploys quantised deep learning models directly on microcontroller-class hardware using model pruning and 8-bit integer quantisation [2]. Both approaches carry fundamental dependencies: level-crossing ADCs require bespoke analogue front-end silicon; TinyML detectors require large labelled training datasets, careful per-device quantisation validation, and typically substantial engineering effort per target platform.

The Min-Max pipeline requires none of these prerequisites. It operates on standard Nyquist-sampled ADC output, applies a deterministic block-wise max/min extraction requiring only integer comparisons, and produces a sparse representation compatible with any microcontroller without specialised DSP instructions. The Real-Time Factors reported here (exceeding $868,000\times$) indicate that the complete pipeline could execute on an ARM Cortex-M class processor at a fraction of its available duty cycle, leaving substantial headroom for wireless transmission, data compression, and triggered morphological analysis. Critically, the pipeline is training-free: its parameters are fixed after a single offline surrogate optimisation pass and require no per-patient or per-device adaptation.

D. Statistical Considerations

The global aggregate F1, computed by summing TP, FP, and FN across all records before computing the ratio is adopted as

the primary performance metric, as it weights each beat equally and avoids the ratio-averaging bias that arises when short records contribute disproportionately to a per-record mean [9].

The one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test is reported as a secondary confirmatory statistic. One interpretive nuance warrants explicit acknowledgement: on databases where both methods approach performance ceilings (MITDB, QTDB), per-record F1 differences are dominated by sub-0.1% marginal wins and ties, making the Wilcoxon test underpowered to detect the direction of change even when the global $\Delta F1$ is positive and meaningful. Non-significant Wilcoxon p-values on near-ceiling databases therefore should not be interpreted as evidence of equivalence; they reflect the limited dynamic range of the test in the ceiling regime. Conversely, statistically significant results on NSTDB ($p < 0.001$ for MinEl; $p = 0.002$ for TiTen) and EDB ($p = 0.002$ for MinEl) are supported by both large global $\Delta F1$ magnitudes and consistent per-record directionality, constituting robust combined evidence of genuine improvement.

E. The Generalization-Specialization Trade-off in Corpus Design

The minor F1 deficits of MinEl on MITDB (-0.42% , $p = 0.999$) and TWADB (-0.29% , $p = 0.996$) deserve contextualization rather than treatment as performance failures. The original Elgendi algorithm [9] was explicitly optimized on the MITDB, and a MITDB-only optimization of MinEl recovers full parity on that database. The decision to instead optimize on a combined MITDB + QTDB + NSTDB corpus was deliberate: it sacrifices a marginal and statistically insignificant quantity on a database where near-ceiling performance is already established, in exchange for meaningful and significant gains on other databases (NSTDB: $+2.49\%$, $p < 0.001$; EDB: $+0.48\%$, $p = 0.021$) where the clinical stakes are substantially higher. The substantial improvement of the kept out EDB confirms that the choice is sound.

F. Limitations and Boundary Conditions

Despite these advances, three critical boundary conditions must be acknowledged to guide future silicon translation:

Silicon Validation and Fixed-Point Arithmetic: All benchmarks were obtained from floating-point MATLAB R2024a executions on a MacBook Pro M1 Max. True edge viability requires translation to fixed-point C or RISC-V assembly and profiling on an ARM Cortex-M or ultra-low-power MCU, where integer arithmetic, memory-fetch overhead, and cache behavior dominate the energy-per-beat budget. The 7-bit block index storage identified in Section II-B provides a concrete starting point: the complete sparse representation for a 10-second window requires fewer than 200 bytes at 10 Hz, which is compatible with the severely constrained SRAM of implantable loop recorders. Fixed-point translation is the single most important next step for demonstrating deployment viability on clinical-grade hardware.

Single-Lead vs. Spatial Fusion: The framework operates on single-lead vectors, consistent with implantable loop recorders and single-lead wearable patches. Extending Min-

Max extraction to a multi-lead architecture (ex. selecting the spatially consistent extremum across leads within each block) could leverage cross-lead correlation to reject localized motion artifacts that manifest as extrema in one lead but not others. This extension is feasible within the same classical framework and does not require additional training data.

The Morphological Boundary: The 10 Hz sparse representation preserves R-peak timing and amplitude but discards the dense inter-sample structure required for clinical waveform analysis: ST-segment elevation measurement, QT-interval computation, and P-wave delineation all require sampling at ≥ 250 Hz per AHA/ACCF/HRS guidelines [3][4]. The pipeline is explicitly scoped to beat detection and HRV-class applications. A natural future architecture is an interrupt-driven two-tier system in which the sparse 10 Hz detector operates as a low-power watchdog and triggers a high-rate buffer capture only upon detection of an anomalous RR interval or a borderline-width complex flagged by the TiTen heuristic. This mirrors the operational logic of existing implantable loop recorders but replaces fixed hardware comparators with an adaptive software-defined detector.

V. CONCLUSION

We have shown that morphology-aware sparse sampling is not a compromise, but a strategic advantage for continuous beat detection. By aligning the sampling strategy with the physiological structure of the ECG, preserving only the extrema that define depolarization events, the proposed pipeline achieves higher accuracy, greater cross-patient reliability, and orders-of-magnitude efficiency gains over native-rate baselines. As wearable and implantable cardiac monitors proliferate, such co-design of signal acquisition and analysis will be essential to deliver clinically robust, battery-conscious monitoring at scale.

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